

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka, Mangalore – 574 146, Phone :0824-2477456

(State Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013 empowered to award degrees under Section 22 of UGC Act of UGC, New Delhi, & Member of Association of Indian Universities, New Delhi)

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ACADEMIC REGULATIONS PERTAINING TO BACHELOR OF ARTS

(B.A. IN JOURNALISM & MASS COMMUNICATION)

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

(2020 ONWARDS)

1 PREAMBLE

The University Grants Commission, New Delhi in its tenth plan guidelines directed the Universities in the country to implement the credit-based semester scheme in both under-graduate and post-graduate programmes. The Credit Based Semester Scheme, makes the product of a University at par with the global practices in terms of academic standards and evaluation strategies. In the emerging scenario of Internationalization of Indian Higher Education, it is imperative that the Universities in India should follow this system so that the mobility of their products both within and across the geographical jurisdiction becomes possible.

Srinivas University aims to achieve academic excellence by providing multi-faceted education to the students and encourage them to reach the pinnacle of success. The University has designed a system that would provide rigorous academic training and necessary skills to enable them to excel in their careers.

Srinivas University is committed to provide a conducive learning environment which ensures comprehensive development of students and make them competent, confident, and good citizens. The objective of the Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (BA in Journalism and Mass Communication) Under Graduate Programme of Srinivas University designed for those students with aptitude and interest in investigation and reporting of current and past issues to the vast audience through Newspapers, Magazines, Televisions, Radio, internet etc.

2. TITLE

These regulations shall be cited as Academic Regulations Pertaining to Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (B.A. in Journalism and Mass Communication), 2019 - 20 onwards.

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Regulation

R1. EXTENT OF APPLICATION

These regulations will apply to Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (BA in Journalism and Mass Communication), 2019 - 20 onwards, having approval of the University /UGC as the case may be.

R2. PROGRAMME OBJECTIVE

The objective of the Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (BA in Journalism and Mass Communication) Programme of Srinivas University is the Under Graduate programme designed for those students with aptitude and interest in investigation and reporting of current and past issues to the vast audience through Newspapers, Magazines, Television, Radio, Internet etc. Journalism Profession correspond information between the News Agencies and Public on the standards of Truth, Autonomy and Transparency. The profession extensively uses Mass Communication Medias such as Radio, Television, Blogs, Portals, Social Networking etc. A Journalist or Writer works in the areas of Business, Culture, Governance, Finance, History, Games, Sports, Politics, Religion, Entertainment, Current Affairs etc. This course has been designed to enrich the skills of enrolled students in the fields of editing, writing, photography, analysis, research, reporting, comprehension etc.

R3. MINIMUM ELIGIBILITY FOR ADMISSION

A candidate who has passed 12th class examination on 10+2 pattern or equivalent from any recognized Pre-University Education Board or any other examination considered as equivalent thereto by Srinivas University is eligible for admission for Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (BA in Journalism and Mass Communication) programme

R4. ADMISSION PROCEDURE

All admissions shall be made through an entrance test conducted by appropriate body as approved by Srinivas University from time to time.

R5. DURATION OF THE PROGRAMME AND MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION

The duration of Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (BA in Journalism and Mass Communication) Programme, shall extend over six semesters (three

academic years). Medium of instruction for all subjects and examination shall be English only, except languages if any.

R6. TIME LIMIT FOR COMPLETION

The candidate shall complete the Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (BA in Journalism and Mass Communication) Programme within eight years from the date of registration in the programme. The term completing the programme means passing all the prescribed examinations of the programme to become eligible for the degree.

R7. ATTENDANCE

No candidate shall be considered to have pursued a regular course of study unless he/she is certified to have attended 75% of the total number of class room sessions conducted in each semester in each paper during his/her course of study. Any student not complying with this requirement shall not be allowed to appear in the semester examinations.

A student not allowed to appear in the preceding semester examinations due to shortage of attendance, may appear in the papers of the preceding semester along with the papers of the current semester after making up the shortfall in the attendance.

R8. COURSES, CREDITS AND SPECIALISATIONS

As per Annexure A.

SUMMARY OF BA BACHELOR OF ARTS IN JOURNALISM AND MASS COMMUNICATION

SEMESTER	TOTAL MARKS	TOTAL CREDITS
SEMESTER I	700	28
SEMESTER II	700	28
SEMESTER III	700	28
SEMESTER IV	700	28
SEMESTER V	700	28
SEMESTER VI	700	20
	4200	160

9. PROJECT WORK

Candidates should undertake projects during the Bachelor of Arts in Journalism and Mass Communication (BA in Journalism and Mass Communication) in their respected area of specialization.

Research Based Project: Every student is required to work on a project in the area of his/her specialization and prepare a dissertation report under the supervision of a Faculty guide and Industry/Company Guide. Prior to the actual work, the students are required to submit a synopsis of the dissertation incorporating the statement of problem, objectives, and methodology to be followed and submit the same to the faculty guide.

The dissertation duly signed by the guides and certified by the principal/director is to be submitted in a bound copy and a soft copy to the university at the end of the VI semester before the commencement of the semester examination. The dissertation shall carry 700 marks in total (Report and Viva-Voce). The dissertation shall be evaluated for 500 marks by examiners (One of them will be the faculty member who has guided the work and other will be the external examiner appointed by the BOE). There shall be a viva-voce examination for 200 marks on the dissertation, and viva-voce will be conducted by internal and external examiners authorized by Chairman of BOE. Detailed guidelines will be issued by UG Department from time to time.

R10. SCHEME OF EXAMINATION

Written Examinations shall be conducted at the end of each Semester as per the Academic Calendar notified in advance. Each course will carry 100 marks of which 50 marks shall be reserved for internal assessment and the remaining 50 marks for written examination to be held at the end of each semester.

The internal assessment marks shall be based on factors such as:

- Two Internal Examinations Conducted by the college.
- Participation in case studies/ discussion, seminars, and group activities;
- Submission of written assignments in scheduled time.
- Class attendance.
- The weightage given to each of these factors shall be decided and announced at the beginning of the semester by the individual teacher responsible for the paper, and the marks obtained shall be made open to the students and shown separately in the mark sheet.

R11. REGISTRATION FOR EXAMINATION:

A candidate shall register for all the papers of the semester when he/she appears for the examination of that semester for the first time.

R12. CARRY OVER PROVISION:

Candidates who fail the lower examinations may take higher semester examinations. The results of candidates who have passed the Sixth/Eight semester examination, but not passed all the examinations of the earlier semesters shall be

announced as NCL (not completed lower examination). Such candidates shall be eligible for the degree only after completion of all the earlier examinations.

R13. STANDARD OF PASSING

The minimum marks for passing the examination for each semester shall be 50% in aggregate and a minimum of 50% marks in each paper.

R.14.0 Course Wise Grading of Students

Letter Grades and Grade Points (GP) Based on the semester performance, each student is awarded a final letter grade at the end of the semester in each Course. The letter grades and the corresponding grade points are as follows:

R.14.1 The Srinivas University adopts absolute grading system wherein the marks are converted to grades, and every semester result will be declared with semester grade point average (SGPA) and Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA). The CGPA will be calculated every semester, except the first semester.

ii. The grading system is with the following letter grades as given below:

Grades and Grade Points

Level	Out Standing	Excellent	Very good	Good	Above Average	Average	Poor	Fail
Letter Grade	O	S	A	B	C	D	E	F
Grade Points	10	09	08	07	06	05	04	00

A student obtaining Grade “F” shall be considered failed and will be required to reappear in the examination.

Such students after passing the failed subject in subsequent examination/s will be awarded with “E” grade irrespective of marks he/she scores in the subsequent examination/s.

Number of attempts taken to clear a subject/s shall be shown in the transcripts.

Level	Out Standing	Excellent	Very good	Good	Above Average	Average	Poor	Fail
Letter Grade	O	S	A	B	C	D	E	F
Grade Points	10	09	08	07	06	05	04	00
Score (Marks) Range (%)	≥ 90	<90	$<80 \geq 70$	$<70 \geq 65$	$<65 \geq 60$	$<60 \geq 55$	$<55 \geq 50$	<50

Computation of SGPA and CGPA

The following procedure to compute the Semester Grade Point Average (SGPA) and Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA):

i. The SGPA is the ratio of sum of the product of the number of credits with the grade points scored by a student in all the courses taken by a student and the sum of the number of credits of all the courses undergone by a student, i.e.

$$SGPA (S_i) = \sum (C_i \times G_i) / \sum C_i$$

where C_i is the number of credits of the i th course and G_i is the grade point scored by the student in the i th course.

ii. The CGPA is also calculated in the same manner taking into account all the courses undergone by a student over all the semesters of a programme, i.e.

$$CGPA = \sum (C_i \times S_i) / \sum C_i$$

where S_i is the SGPA of the i th semester and C_i is the total number of credits in that semester.

iii. The SGPA and CGPA shall be rounded off to 2 decimal places and reported in the transcripts.

Illustration for computation of SGP and CGPA

Computation of SGPA

Illustration No.1

Course	Credit	Grade Letter	Grade Point	Credit Point (Credit x Grade)
Course 1	4	A	8	4x8 = 32
Course 2	4	C	6	4x6 = 24
Course 3	4	B	7	4x7 = 28
Course 4	4	O	10	4x10 = 40
Course 5	4	D	5	4x5 = 20
Course 6	4	C	6	4x6 = 24
Course 7	2	S	9	2x9 = 18
Course 8	2	C	6	2x6 = 12
	28			198

Thus, $SGPA = 198/28 = 7.071$

Illustration No.2

Course	Credit	Grade Letter	Grade Point	Credit Point (Credit x Grade)
Course 1	4	A	8	4x8 = 32
Course 2	4	C	6	4x6 = 24
Course 3	4	B	7	4x7 = 28
Course 4	4	O	10	4x10 = 40
Course 5	4	F	0	4x0 = 00
Course 6	4	C	6	4x6 = 24
Course 7	2	S	9	2x9 = 18
Course 8	2	C	6	2x6 = 12
	28			178

Thus, SGPA = $178/28 = 6.357$

Illustration No.2(a)

Course	Credit	Grade Letter	Grade Point	Credit Point (Credit x Grade)
Course 5	4	E	4	4x4 = 16
	28			Ci (First Attempt 178 + Ci Subsequent attempt 16 = 194

Thus, SGPA = $194/28 = 6.928$

Illustration No.3

Course	Credit	Grade Letter	Grade Point	Credit Point (Credit x Grade)
Course 1	4	A	8	4x8 = 32
Course 2	4	C	6	4x6 = 24
Course 3	4	B	7	4x7 = 28
Course 4	4	O	10	4x10 = 40
Course 5	4	S	9	4x9 = 36
Course 6	4	C	6	4x6 = 24
Course 7	2	S	9	2x9 = 18
Course 8	2	C	6	2x6 = 12
	28			214

Thus, SGPA = $214/28 = 7.642$

CGPA = $\frac{28 \times 6.928 + 28 \times 7.642}{28} = 7.285$

CGPA after Final Semester (in Six semester programme)

Sem.1	Sem 2	Sem 3	Sem 4	Sem 5	Sem6
Credit 28	Credit 28	Credit 28	Credit 28	Credit 28	Credit 20
SGPA 7	SGPA 8.5	SGPA 6.86	SGPA 9.2	SGPA 8.5	SGPA 7.2

$$\text{Thus, CGPA} = \frac{28 \times 7 + 28 \times 8.5 + 28 \times 6.86 + 28 \times 9.2 + 28 \times 8.5 + 20 \times 7.2}{160} = 7.91$$

CGPA after Final Semester (in Eight semester programme)

Sem. 1	Sem 2	Sem 3	Sem 4	Sem 5	Sem 6	Sem 7	Sem 8
Cred it 28	Cred it 14						
S G P A							
7	8 . 5	6 . 8 6	9 . 2	9 . 2	8 . 5	7	6 . 5

$$\text{Thus, CGPA} = \frac{28 \times 7 + 28 \times 8.5 + 28 \times 6.86 + 28 \times 9.2 + 28 \times 9.2 + 28 \times 8.5 + 28 \times 7 + 14 \times 6.5}{210} = 7.93$$

210

Transcript (Format): Based on the above recommendations on Letter grades, grade points, SGPA and CCPA, the transcript for each semester and a consolidated transcript indicating the performance in all semesters may be issued.

R14.2 CONVERSION OF GRADES INTO PERCENTAGE:

Conversion formula for the conversion of GPA into Percentage is

$$[\text{CGPA Earned} - 0.75] \times 10 = \text{Percentage of marks scored.}$$

Illustration: $[\text{CGPA Earned } 7.93 - 0.75] \times 10 = 71.8\%$

R.14.3 A student is considered to have completed a Course successfully or achieved a pass grade and earned the credits if he / she secures a letter grade other than U or W or I or F in that Course. A letter grade U or W or I or F in any Course implies a failure in that Course.

R.14.4 A Course successfully completed cannot be repeated.

R.14.5 If a student gets a fail grade F (U/W/I) in a course with both theory and practical components, then he/she has to reappear in the end semester examinations of both.

R.14.6 If a student obtains U grade in a course in the first three attempts, from fourth attempt onwards, full weightage (100%) shall be assigned to marks scored in the end semester examinations and the internal assessment marks they have scored during the regular course of study will be ignored. The first attempt is that which corresponds to the first registration for the course. If a student gets U or I or W grade in an attempt that is treated as an attempt.

The detailed methodology of normalization of internal marks as well as marks in the end-semester examinations shall be formulated by the Controller of Examinations.

R.14.7 To pass in a course with earnable credits a student has to score a minimum of 50% of the total normalized marks.

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COLLEGE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore- 575 001. Phone: 0824-2441022

B.A. (JOURNALISM & MASS COMMUNICATION)

Duration: 3 Years, Six Semesters. (Admissions open for the batch 2019-20)

Eligibility: Pass in 10+2/12th Standard with minimum 40 % marks.

Admission needs valid score in **SUAT**.

About B.A. (Journalism & Mass Communication)

The Bachelor of Arts (B.A.) Journalism & Mass Communication is an under graduate programme designed for those students with aptitude and interest in investigation and reporting of current and past issues to the vast audience through Newspapers, Magazines, Television, Radio, Internet etc. Journalism Profession correspond information between the News Agencies and Public on the standards of Truth, Autonomy and Transparency. The profession extensively uses Mass Communication Medias such as Radio, Television, Blogs, Portals, Social Networking etc. A Journalist or Writer works in the areas of Business, Culture, Governance, Finance, History, Games, Sports, Politics, Religion, Entertainment, Current Affairs etc. This course has been designed to enrich the skills of enrolled students in the fields of editing, writing, photography, analysis, research, reporting, comprehension etc.

Special Features of the Programme

- Classes will be held from 9.00 a.m. to 2.00 p.m. with half an hour break during week days.
- E-Study material will be provided from the college for every subject according to the syllabus.
- Industry oriented syllabus with special focus on experimental learning.
- Mini Project in each semester.
- Innovations in Examination System with opportunity for personal seeing of evaluated papers.
- Make up exams in every semester to avoid year loss.
- Placement support and research oriented projects for every student.
- Focus on smart skill development & training on competitive exams.
- Opportunity to visit various News Agencies
- Separate Hostel & Transport facility for Boys & Girls.
- Further opportunity to do Post Graduation, M. Phil., & Ph.D. Programmes.

Career Opportunities

News Reporter, News Reader, Feature Writer, Columnist, Fashion Photographer, News Analyst, Public Relations Officer, Radio Jockey (RJ), Special Correspondent, Video Jockey (VJ), TV Correspondent, Freelance Writer, Correspondent, Illustrator, Photo Journalist, Journalist, Associate Editor, Cartoonist, Columnist, Proof Reader, Sub Editor, Writer, Publisher, Telecasting Assistant, Researcher, Transmission Executive.

Programme Structure

SEMESTER 1			SEMESTER 2		
SN	Subject	Marks	SN	Subject	Marks
1	Fundamentals of Journalism	100	1	Editing	100
2	Reporting	100	2	Media & Environment	100
3	Business Communication I	100	3	Business Communication II	100
4	Micro Economics	100	4	Macro Economics	100
5	Organisational Behaviour	100	5	Human Resource Management	100
6	Indian Constitution & Environmental Studies	100	6	Marketing Management	100
7	ESEP	50	7	Soft Skill Training	50
8	Visit to domestic News Houses/ Agencies / Publisher	50	8	ESEP	50
		700			700
SEMESTER 3			SEMESTER 4		
1	Print Journalism	100	1	Electronic Journalism	100
2	Advertisement	100	2	New Media Technology	100
3	Human Right Journalism	100	3	Photo Journalism	100
4	Feature Writing	100	4	Media Law	100
5	Management Information System	100	5	E Business	100
6	Product & Brand Management	100	6	Global Business Management	100
7	Cyber Law and Security analysis	50	7	Feature Writing – Practical	50
8	ESEP	50	8	ESEP	50
		700			700
SEMESTER 5			SEMESTER 6		
1	Public Relation	100	1	Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce	700
2	Basic Media Research	100			
3	Film Production	100			
4	Magazine Journalism	100			
5	Television Production	100			
6	Entrepreneurship Development	100			
7	Checking Plagiarism	50			
8	Press Report Practical	50			
		700			700

**JOIN ABOVE INNOVATIVE B.A. (Journalism & Mass Communication) WITH
INDUSTRY RELEVANCE AND JOB ORIENTED SYLLABUS
TO RE-DEFINE YOUR CAREER ALTITUTDE**

CREATING INNOVATORS

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Educating the Next Generation

COURSE STRUCTURE

SEMETER 1	SEMESTER 2
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fundamentals of Journalism 2. Reporting 3. Business Communication I 4. Micro Economics 5. Organisational Behaviour 6. Indian Constitution & Environmental Studies 7. Visit to domestic News Houses/ Agencies / Publisher 8. ESEP 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Editing 2. Media & Environment 3. Business Communication II 4. Macro Economics 5. Human Resource Management 6. Marketing Management 7. Soft Skill Training 8. ESEP
Total - 700 marks	Total - 700 marks
SEMETER 3	SEMESTER 4
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Print Journalism 2. Advertisement 3. Human Right Journalism 4. Feature Writing 5. Management Information System 6. Product & Brand Management 7. Cyber Law and Security analysis 8. ESEP 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Electronic Journalism 2. New Media Technology 3. Photo Journalism 4. Media Law 5. E Business 6. Global Business Management 7. Feature Writing – Practical 8. ESEP
Total - 700 marks	Total – 700 marks
SEMETER 5	SEMETER 6
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Public Relation 2. Basic Media Research 3. Film Production 4. Magazine Journalism 5. Television Production 6. Entrepreneurship Development 7. Checking Plagiarism 8. Press Report Practical 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internship & Dissertation. To produce a news magazine & Viva – Voce
Total – 700 marks	Total – 700 marks

I SEMESTER

Subject Code	Subjects	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/ week	Credits
20BAJ11	Business Communication I	100	04	04
20BAJ12	Micro Economics	100	04	04
20BAJ13	Fundamentals of Journalism	100	04	04
20BAJ14	Organisational Behaviour	100	04	04
20BAJ15	Reporting	100	04	04
20BAJ16	Indian Constitution & Environmental Studies	100	04	04
20BAJ17	ESEP	50	02	02
20BAJ18	Visit to domestic News Houses/ Agencies / Publisher	50	02	02
Total Credits				28

II SEMESTER

Subject Code	Subjects	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/ week	Credits
20BAJ21	Business Communication II	100	04	04
20BAJ22	Macro Economics	100	04	04
20BAJ23	Human Resource Management	100	04	04
20BAJ24	Marketing Management	100	04	04
20BAJ25	Editing	100	04	04
20BAJ26	Media & Environment	100	04	04
20BAJ27	Soft Skill Training	50	02	02
20BAJ28	ESEP	50	02	02
Total Credits				28

III SEMESTER

Subject Code	Subjects	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/week	Credits
20BAJ31	Print Journalism	100	04	04
20BAJ32	Advertisement	100	04	04
20BAJ33	Product & Brand Management	100	04	04
20BAJ34	Feature Writing	100	04	04
20BAJ35	Human Right Journalism	100	04	04
20BAJ36	Management Information System	100	04	04
20BAJ37	Cyber Law and Security analysis	50	02	02
20BAJ38	ESEP	50	02	02
Total Credits				28

IV SEMESTER

Subject Code	Subjects	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/week	Credits
20BAJ41	Electronic Journalism	100	04	04
20BAJ42	New Media Technology	100	04	04
20BAJ43	E Business	100	04	04
20BAJ44	Global Business Management	100	04	04
20BAJ45	Photo Journalism	100	04	04
20BAJ46	Media Law	100	04	04
20BAJ47	Feature Writing – Practical	50	02	02
20BAJ48	ESEP	50	02	02
Total Credits				28

V SEMESTER

Subject Code	Subjects	Total Marks	Hours of Teaching/ week	Credits
20BAJ51	Public Relation	100	04	04
20BAJ52	Basic Media Research	100	04	04
20BAJ53	Film Production	100	04	04
20BAJ54	Magazine Journalism	100	04	04
20BAJ55	Television Production	100	04	04
20BAJ56	Entrepreneurship Development	100	04	04
20BAJ57	Checking Plagiarism	50	02	02
20BAJ58	Press Report Practical	50	02	02
Total Credits				28

VI SEMESTER

Subject Code	Subjects	Total Marks
20BAJ61	Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce	700
Total Credits		700

I Semester

20BAJ11: BUSINESS COMMUNICATION I

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: To put in use the basic mechanics of Grammar. And to provide an outline to effective Organisational Communication.

UNIT I: Basics of Functional English

An Introduction of the Structures in English Language, Types and Construction of Sentences, Usage of Parts of Speech and Linkers, Usage of Idioms and Phrases for Standardising Communication, Accent and Pronunciation for Effective Communication, Explicit Comprehensive Exercises, Implicit Comprehensive Exercises, Converting Titles into meaningful passages.

UNIT II: Foundations of Business Communications

Communication and its Process Flow, Types, Forms or Categories of Communication, Verbal, Non-verbal, Formal, Informal, external, internal, inward, outward Barriers to Communication and steps to overcome them, Effective Reading Skills Basics, significance and reading practice, Basic Visual and Listening Skills, Observation, Focus and Concentration building, Conversation and Language Skills, Dialogues, Rhetoric's and Passages, Non-Verbal communication and its effects, Body-Language, Professional Manners, Etiquettes and Behaviour, Cultural differences and Diversity in Communication.

UNIT III: Essentials of Professional Writings

Introduction to Writing and Keyboard Typing Skills, Types and Kinds of Business Writings, Structure of Keyboard and typing practice, Important varieties of Business Letters and Requests, Routine letters and Positive messages, Placing Orders, Directives and Instructions, Information requests, Bad News and Persuasion Letters, Communication of Negatives and unpleasant updates/developments, Sales Letters, Collection letters, Job application letters. Types of Professional Writing Formats Block and Indented, Key points to remember while writing Business Letter or Requests, Understanding Emails and Professional Chat, SMS communications. Writing Reports and its needs, Types of Reports, Important classifications, varieties and kinds of professional reports, Structure & Components of Reports.

UNIT IV: Advanced Written Communications and Designing and Delivering Oral Presentations

Fundamentals of Business Writing- Introduction- ABC3 Model of Writing- Writing agenda and minutes for Meetings, Meaning, significance and needs, designing and formulation, applications. Drafting Notices and Memorandum - Importance, Formalities and Protocols. Challenges in Professional Presentations- Process of Making Effective Presentations- Collaborative Presentations- Online Presentations-Presenting to a Culturally Diverse Audience

UNIT V: Communicating Through Technology and Employment Communication

Introduction- Classification of Technological Tools for Communication- Major Technological Tools- Effective Use of Technology for Communication- Communicating Through Social Media-Communicating in Virtual Teams.

Employment Process- Setting Goals- Understanding Employers' Mindset towards the Employment Process- Organizing Your Approach to the Employment Process- Drafting Résumés and Other Employment Messages- Drafting Application Letters- Handling Group Discussions- Handling Interviews- Drafting Post-Interview Employment Messages.

Books of Reference:

- J. C. Good English (Getting it Right) -Ajmani
- Essentials of Business Writing -Guffey, Mary Ellen
- Jr. Report Writing for Business -Lesikar, Raymond V., & John D. Pettit
- Writing Reports - Seely, John
- Business Correspondence and Report Writing-Sharma, R. C. & Krishna Mohan
- Business Communication: A Practice Oriented Approach- Shalini Kalia

220BAJ12: MICRO ECONOMICS

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Over the course the student will learn to formalize economic phenomena and gain an understanding of their workings.

UNIT I: Introduction of Micro Economics

Definition and Nature, Scope, Importance and Limitations. Basic Economic Problems, Market forces in solving Economic Problems.

UNIT II: Demand Analysis

Meaning of Demand, Determinants of Demand, Law of Demand, Introduction to elasticity of demand, Price Elasticity of Demand, Degree of Price Elasticity of Demand, Measurement of Price elasticity, Income Elasticity of Demand, Kinds of Income Elasticity of Demand.

UNIT III: Supply Analysis

Meaning and Definition, Law of Supply, Factors affecting Supply, Elasticity of Supply, Market Mechanism, Short run Vs. Long run Elasticities of supply- Price Control.

UNIT IV: Cost Analysis

Accounting Costs and Economic Costs, Short Run Cost Analysis - Fixed, Variable, Total Cost Curves, Average and Marginal Costs, Long Run Cost Analysis, The constitutional environment, rationale, and extent of state intervention.

UNIT V: Pricing Under Various Market Conditions

Perfect Competition - Equilibrium of Firm and Industry under Perfect Competition, Monopoly - Price Determination under Monopoly, Monopolistic Competition - Price and Output Determination under Monopolistic Competition.

Books for Reference:

- Textbook of Economic Theory - Stonier and Hague
- Introduction to Positive Economics - Richard G. Lipsey
- Business Economics (Micro) - Dr.Girijashankar
- Micro Economics - M. L. Seth
- Micro Economics - M. L. Jhingan
- Managerial Economics - D. M. Mithani

OBAJ13: Fundamentals of Journalism

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: To understand the importance, functions & scope of communication and media. To describe the growth and development of communication and media. To understand the periodic changes in the media.

UNIT I: Journalism

Introduction to Journalism: Nature, Scope and definition of journalism, what is Journalism? Is it a craft? a profession or an industry? Role and responsibilities of a Journalist, what are Mass Media? Theories of the Press Communication, Public opinion and democracy.

UNIT II: Journalism as a profession

Journalist – Their role and responsibilities, Indian Constitution and freedom of press, Careers in Journalism and mass media. Professional organisations in Media

UNIT III: Press in India

A brief Review of the Evolution of Indian Press, with reference to J A Hickey, Raja Ram Mohan Roy, James Silk Buckingham, M K Gandhi, S. Sadanand and B G Horniman, Kannada Journalism: Origin, Growth and Development.

UNIT IV: News and Newspaper

News: Meaning & definition, Sources and elements of news, Characteristics of news. Mass Communication: Concept & Characteristics. Different styles of news writing in Newspaper. News Agencies, Photo Journalism. Cartoons

Unit V: Use of Technology

Printing technology and production methods, Photography: Camera, Lens, Depth of Field. Page design, Cartoon, Color Techniques.

Books for Reference

- B N Ahuja: History of Indian Press – Growth of Newspapers in India, Surjeet Publications, Delhi, 2009
- D S Mehta: Mass Communication and Journalism in India, Aliied Publishers Pvt Ltd., Mumbai, 2006
- William L. Rivers: The Mass Media: Reporting Writing Editing, Harper & Row, 1975
- F. Fraser Bond: An Introduction to Journalism, The Macmillan Company, 1954
- Nadig Krishnamurthy: Indian Journalism, Prasaranga, Mysore University, Mysore, 1966
- Rangaswami Parthasarathy: Journalism in India, Sterling Publications Pvt. Ltd., 1997

20BAJ 14: ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: To help the students to develop cognizance of the importance of human behaviour. And to enable students to describe how people behave under different conditions and understand why people behave as they do.

UNIT I: Introduction to Organizational Behaviour

Introduction- Meaning-Definition- Need and Importance of OB – Historical roots of OB- Nature and Scope of OB- OB Models, S-O-B-C Model. Role of OB in Management of business, Challenges, and opportunities for managers in OB.

UNIT II: Perception, Leadership, and Power

Meaning- Definition- Factors influencing Perception- Perceptual Process- Attribution- Errors in Perception-Managing perception. Leadership- Meaning- Importance- Leadership Styles-theories of Leadership- leaders Vs managers- Contemporary issues in leadership Power- Definition, types of power- sources of Power-Power Tactics- Power centres.

UNIT III: Group dynamics and Attitudes

Group Dynamics- meaning, features and Importance of Groups- Reasons for formation of group- Types of Groups- group Norms- Group Cohesion. Group Behaviour- Organisation structure. Attitude- meaning, Characteristics- Importance of Attitude in an organization- Components of Attitude- Relationship between Attitude and Behaviour- Barriers to Changing Attitude.

UNIT IV: ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND CHANGE

Meaning and nature of Organisational Culture- Functions of Organisational Culture- Types of Culture- Creating and maintaining organizational culture. Organisational Change- Meaning, Definition and Nature of organizational Change, Types of Organisational Change- Kurt Lewin's three step model- Seven stage model of change- Kotter's Eight step plan for implementing change- Methods of Implementing Organisational Change.

UNIT V: PERSONALITY AND PRACTICAL COMPONENTS OF OB

Personality-Meaning-Definition-Types- factors influencing Personality- Personality Traits- Determinants of Personality- Theories of Personality (Type Theory, Trait Theory, Intrapsychic Theory, Social Learning, and Self Theory).

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Organizational Behaviour - Stephen P. Robins-
- Organizational Behavior - M.N. Mishra
- Organizational Behavior - K. Ashwathappa
- Change and Knowledge Management - Janakiram, Ravindra, ShubhaMuralidhar.
- Organizational Behavior - Niraj Kumar
- Organizational Behavior - Fred Luthans

20BAJ15: REPORTING

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objectives: Information dissemination across traditional and digital publication platforms demands accuracy and fairness that act as the hallmark of writing professionals. Students will understand how writing is delivered across various verticals

UNIT I: News

News – definitions – news values – elements of news – sources of news Structure of a news story – lead, types of leads- body.

UNIT II: Reporting for Media

Reporting for print – radio – television and new media- Package stories for TV, Attributes of a reporter- media convergence.

UNIT III: News Stories

Types of news stories – crime – court – legislature – politics – culture – environment – sports – investigative - mofussil reporting and development reporting.

UNIT IV: Techniques of reporting

Press conferences, interviews, types and techniques, press release, reporting for news agencies.

UNIT V: Challenges of Reporting

New trends in reporting, Mobile journalism, citizen journalism.

Books for reference

- Barnas, Frank. (2017). *Broadcast news writing, reporting and producing*. New York: Routledge.
- James G. Stovall (2014). *Writing for the Mass Media*. Indianapolis: Pearson Educations.
- Mencher, Melvin. (2006). *Melvin Mencher's news reporting and writing*. Boston: McGraw- Hill
- Phillips, Angela. (2007). *Good Writing for Journalists*. New Delhi: Sage
- Rajan, Nalini. (2007). *21st Century Journalism in India*. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
- Sharma, Diwakar. (2005). *Modern journalism: Reporting and writing*. New Delhi: Deep & Deep.
- Shrivastava, K.M. (2015). *News reporting and editing*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.
- Steen, Rob. (2008). *Sports journalism*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Strentz Herbert. (2002). *News reporting and news sources*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall.

20BAJ16: INDIAN CONSTITUTION & ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: To Enable the student to understand the importance of constitution and to understand the structure of executive, legislature and judiciary

UNIT I: Introduction

Introduction to the Constitution of India, Nature of the Indian Constitution, Significance of the Indian Constitution, The Making of the Constitution and Salient features of the Constitution, Preamble of the Indian Constitution, Citizenship

UNIT II: Rights and Freedom

Fundamental Rights- Right to Equality, Right to Freedom, Protection of Life and Personal Liberty, Right against Exploitation, Right to Freedom of Religion, Cultural and educational rights and right to Constitutional Remedies. Directive Principles of State Policy & Fundamental Duties, Union Executives – President, Prime Minister and Parliament, State Executives – Governor Chief Minister and State Legislature.

UNIT III: Judicial System:

The Union Judiciary-The supreme court of India, The State Judiciary-The High Court of States. Election Commission of India. The Emergency Provisions and the Amendment of the Constitution.

UNIT IV: Introduction to Environment

Environmental Studies- Introduction, Definition, Nature, Scope and Importance. Eco System- Concept, Structure, Functions and Components of Eco System. Natural Resources- Forest, Water, Mineral, Food, Energy and Land Resources.

UNIT V: Environmental Issues

Environmental Pollution- Meaning, Definition, Causes, Types: Air Pollution, Water Pollution, Soil Pollution, Marine Pollution, Thermal Pollution and Nuclear hazards. Environmental Issues: Climate Change, Global Warming, Acid Rain, Ozone Layer depletion, Nuclear Accident, Bopal Gas Leakage tragedy and Population Explosion. Legal measures- Environmental Protection Act, Constitutional Provisions and Judicial Remedies.

Books for Reference:

- Indian Constitution - D Dbasu
- Constitutional Law of India - J.N. Pandey
- Constitution law of India - M. P. Jain
- The Constitution of India - Dr.ParvathyAppaiha
- Environmental Law and Policy in India - Shyam Divan and Armin Rosencranz
- Environment and Ecology - MajidHussain

II Semester

20BAJ21: BUSINESS COMMUNICATION II

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Understand and demonstrate the use of basic and advanced proper writing techniques that today's technology demands, including anticipating audience reaction.

UNIT 1: FUNDAMENTALS OF ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

Meaning, Need & Significance. Interactions, Speeches and Speaking. Types of Verbal Speeches. Foundations of Public Speaking. Types of Public Speaking. Speech & Elocution Drafting. Public Speaking practicum. Speech Body Language and Non-Verbal Etiquettes

UNIT II: DIALOGUE AND CONVERSATION SKILLS

Need for dialogue and conversation skills, the art of story-telling – Initiation, thought process and delivering techniques. Expressions and Summarizations, Feedback and Reply Skills, Building good speaking manners & etiquette. Debates – Kinds, Professional significance of debates. Group Discussion.

UNIT III: ORAL VERBAL INTERVIEWS AND PRESENTATIONS

Interview Basics and Introduction, Foundations, Mock Interview or Pre-employment testing. Types of Interviews. Giving Opinions – Definitions, Importance and features. Professional Discussions, Conflict Resolutions and Negotiations – Significance and Need, Types of Negotiation Strategies. Managing Stage Presentations. Audio-Visual Mediums in communications. ICT (Information & Communication Technologies) in Presentations.

UNIT IV: PROFESSIONAL MEETINGS AND INTERACTIONS

Meetings (Face to Face and Group) – Need and Significance, Types and Kinds of Meetings. Communicating Minutes and Agenda, Extempore – Meaning, need and significance, Steps in delivery. Oral Commentaries and Narrations, Telephone Conversation Etiquettes. Understanding and Importance of Hotlines, Video-Conferencing – Meaning, need and importance, etiquettes, technicalities. Giving introductory welcome and concluding valedictory address.

UNIT V: PUBLIC RELATIONS (PR)

Meaning and Need, Significance and Objectives. Image Building – Soft Skills, Personal Skills, Sales skills, Self-Organizing. Handling Rhetoric's Press and Media Briefing, Significance of Press and media, Media and Press Communication essentials, Skills Required. Legal aspects of communication – Need and Significance, Practical Scenarios and Cases. Use of mass media for PR, TRP, Coverage, Publicity. Do's and Do not's in PR.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Speech Communication made simple – Paulette Dale, PH.D., James C Wolf
- Public Speaking (An Audience Centred Approach) – Beebe & Steven A.
- Communication Works -Teri Kwai Gamble and Michael Gamble.
- Communicating effectively -Saundra Hybels.
- Communicating for Success – Cheryl Hamilton and Bony Creel.
- Business Communications from Principles to Practice – Matthukutty M. Monipally

20BAJ22: MACRO ECONOMICS

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objectives: This module is designed to introduce learners to the macroeconomic environment and the principles underlying macroeconomic policies and government strategies.

Unit I: Introduction to Macroeconomics

Definition and Nature, Scope, Importance and Limitations, Types of macroeconomics, Static and dynamic analysis of Macroeconomics, Macroeconomics and business environment.

Unit II: Theories of National Income Determination

Keynes Theory of employment, Consumption Function, Investment Function, Concept of Unemployment, Circular flow of Money.

Unit III: Macro Economic Environment

Inflation: Meaning, Types, Cause, Effects, Deflation: Meaning and Effects, Financial Market and Types, Business Cycles: Concept, Features, Phases and Effects.

Unit IV: Public Finance

Meaning of Public Finance, Sources of Revenue: Tax Revenue and Non-Tax Revenue, Public Expenditure: Meaning, Classification and Causes, Public Debt: Concept, Importance and Types

Unit V: India and World Economy

Introduction to India and world Economy, Globalization: Meaning, arguments for and against. Steps in Globalisation, GATT, WTO: Introduction, Objectives, structure and Functions, Impact of WTO on Indian Economy, Make in India Campaign (Introduction)

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Ackley G. – Macro Economics: Theory and Policy, Macmillan Publishing Company, New York.
- Ahuja H. L. – Macro Economics: Theory and Policy, S. Chand & Co. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Gupta S. B. – Monetary Economics, S. Chand and Co. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Shapiro E. – Macro Economic Analysis, Galgotia Publications, New Delhi
- Crowther G. – An Outline of Money.
- Chandler L. V. – The Economics of Money and Banking.

20BAJ23: HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objectives: To enable the students to understand the HR Management and system at various levels in general and in certain specific industries or organizations. It helps the students to focus on and analyse the issues and strategies required to select and develop manpower resources.

UNIT I: INTRODUCTION TO HUMAN RESOURCE MANGEMENT

Definition, Meaning of Human Resource Management, Features, Objectives, Scope, Evolution of HRM, Functions –Managerial – Operative, Role of the HR Manager, Qualities of Human Resource Manager.

UNIT II: JOB ANALYSIS AND HUMAN RESOURCE PLANNING

Job Analysis –Meaning, Job Description- Job specification, Job Design- Techniques, HRP- Meaning, Definition, Objectives, Importance of HRP, Process of HRP, Steps to make HRP Effective.

UNIT III: RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION

Recruitment – Definition, Meaning, Objectives, Factors affecting Recruitment Sources of Recruitment, Selection – Meaning, Essentials, Scientific Selection Process, Placement, Induction.

UNIT IV: ABSENTEESIM AND LABOUR TURNOVER:

Concept of Absenteeism- Meaning, Causes, Effects, Measures to Reduce Absenteeism. Labour Turnover – Meaning, Causes, Effects, Measures to Reduce Labour Turnover.

UNIT V: WAGE AND ADMINISTRATION:

Compensation Administration-Meaning, Objectives, Factors Influencing wage and salary levels, Methods of Wage Payment-Time Wage Payment, Piece Wage Payment, Concept of Minimum Wages, Fair Wages and Living Wages, Fringe Benefits

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Human Resource Management- Text and Cases: VSP Rao
- A Hand Book of Personnel Management Practice: Dale Yolder
- Fundamentals of Human Resource management- T.N. chabra
- Human Resource Management- L.M. Prasad
- Human Resource Management- K.S. Ashwathappa
- Personnel management- C.B.Mamoria
- Personnel and Human Resources Management- P Subba Rao

20BAJ24: MARKETING MANAGEMENT

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Develop an integrated marketing communications plan for a product, concept, good and/or service based on an identified market need or target.

UNIT I: INTRODUCTION TO MARKETING MANAGEMENT AND MARKETING SEGMENTATION

Marketing- Meaning & Definition- Importance & Functions, Concepts of Marketing - Traditional & Modern Concepts, Marketing Management- Meaning, Definition, Importance. **Marketing segmentation**

UNIT II: MARKETING MIX

Product-Meaning, Product Planning-Meaning, Product Mix-Meaning, Product Line-Meaning, Pricing-Meaning, Importance, Methods/Types of Pricing, Place-Distribution-Meaning & definition of channels of distribution & Types of channels, Promotion- Personnel selling, Advertising, Publicity, Public relation, Extended 8 Ps- People, Processes, Physical Evidence and Productivity.

UNIT III: BRANDING, LABELLING & CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

Branding- Meaning, Functions, Advantages & Classification, Packaging- Meaning & Functions, Labelling-Meaning, Product life cycle- Meaning, Stages & its Strategies, New Product Development-Process/Stages, Failure of New Products and its reasons, **Consumer Behaviour:** Meaning, Definition, Importance, Factors affecting consumer behaviour.

UNIT IV: SERVICE AND RURAL MARKETING

Service Marketing: Meaning, Characteristics, Distinction between Marketing of Product & Service, Classification of services (Consumer & Industrial)

Rural Marketing: Meaning, significance, Distinction between Rural markets & urban markets, Problems of Rural Marketing.

UNIT V: RECENT TRENDS IN MARKETING

Recent trends in Modern Marketing- Electronic Marketing, Social Marketing, Tele-Marketing, Viral Marketing, Sustainable Marketing, Relationship Marketing, Customer Relationship Marketing (CRM), & Niche Marketing (Meaning Only), Green Marketing- Meaning, Definition, Benefits, Challenges in Going Green.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Marketing Management: Philip Kotler.
- Marketing Management: Rajan Saxena.
- Marketing Management: N. Sontaki.
- Marketing Management: R.S.N Pillai & Bhagavathi.
- Marketing Management: Arun Kumar & Meenakshi.
- Modern Marketing: B.S. Raman.
- Modern Marketing: S.A. Sherlakar.
- Modern Marketing: Davar.
- Consumer Behaviour: Schiffman & Kabul.
- Marketing Management: Excel Books; Jayachandran & Kazmi

20BAJ25: EDITING

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: This course elucidates on eye for detail while editing and proofing of stories/wire service copies, understanding design elements, layouts, printing parameters, and understanding the technology supporting the print and digital work.

UNIT I: Editing

Nature, process, importance. News room setup, Role and functions of an editor, news editor, sub-editor. Guest editor.

UNIT II: Headline

Headline – functions and types of headline—techniques of writing headlines – trends in headline writing.

UNIT III: Editorial Page

Editorial page – editorials – types of editorial – middles – letters to the editor Op-ed–articles, advertorials.

UNIT IV: Newspaper Design

Techniques of page layout, latest trends in page layout, dummy, pagination, style sheets. Page making softwares : PageMaker, QuarkExpress, Indesign -photo editing.

UNIT V: Editing for electronic Media

Editing for radio and television – Rewriting- translation – types and techniques of translation.

Books for reference

- Brooks, S & Pinson, James L. (2017). *The art of editing in the age of 39onvergence*. New Work: Routledge.
- Ludwig, Mark D. & Gilmore, Gene. (2005). *Modern news editing*: Iowa: Blackwell.
- Ross F.Collins (2013). *Editing Across Media: Content and Process for Print and Online Publication*. McFarland & Co. Inc
- Shrivastava, K.M. (2015). *News reporting and editing*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.
- Prasad, Sharada. (1993). *Editors on editing*. New Delhi: National Book Trust.
- Ravindran, R.K. (1999). *Handbook of reporting and editing*. New Delhi: Anmol Publications.
- Roy, Barun. (2000). *Beginners' guide to journalism*. Delhi: Pustak Mahal.
- Sharma, S. (2006). *Editing, Theory and Practice*. New Delhi: Anmol Publications Pvt Ltd.

20BAJ26: MEDIA AND ENVIRONMENT

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Media and communication play a vital role in understanding the environment, its issues and what comprises it. This course is designed to give insight into how environmental concerns are looked upon, understood, contested and executed on.

Unit I: Introduction to Media and Environment

Environment studies, Environment policies of India, introduction to Environment reporting.

UNIT II: Bio-diversity

Bio-diversity in India, threats to bio-diversity, endangered species, flora and fauna, removable and non-removable resources, equitable use of resources, industrialisation and its impact

UNIT III: Environment, Society and Media

Sustainable development, Environmental ethics, Environment pollution, climate change and impact of climate change

UNIT IV: Issues on Environment

Western Ghats, Issues pertaining to Western Ghats, media coverage of Environment and climate change, displacement and rehabilitation issues

UNIT V: Environmental Activity and Media

Madhav Ghadgil and Kasturi Rangan Reports on Western Ghats, Environment Movements in India, Environment Activism, use of social media and other mediums to voice our opinions

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Allaby, Michael (1997) *Basic Environmental Science*, Routledge,
- Neuzil, Mark; Kovarik, William, (1996) *Mass Media and Environmental Conflict*, Sage Publications,
- Kothari, Asish (1997) *Understanding Biodiversity*, Orient Longman
- Gadgil, Madhav; Guha, Ramachandra (1992) *The fissured land- An ecological history of India*, Oxford University Press,
- Surendra, Lawrence; Schindler, Klaus; Ramaswamy, Prasanna (Editors),(1996) *The Stories They Tell: a Dialogue Among Philosophers Scientists and Environmentalists*, Earthworm Books Pvt Ltd

III Semester

20BAJ31: PRINT JOURNALISM

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: This subject will bring students to create an interest for reading newspapers and magazines to the next level and develop their journalism skills

UNIT I : Evolution of printing

Printing in India, New Techniques in Printing; Types of Printing; Letter Press, Lithography, Intaglio/Gravure, Serigraphy, Photo Composition.

UNIT II: Newspapers in India before independence

Contribution of James Augustus Hickey, James Silk Buckingham, Raja Rammohan Roy. The first war of Indian independence and the Press. Freedom struggle and the Press: B G Tilak, Ghosh brothers, S. Sadanand, Mahatma Gandhi.

UNIT III: Major Indian Newspaper:

Dainik Bhaskar, Dainik Jagran, Hindusthan Dainik, The Times of India, The Hindustan Times, The Statesman, The Hindu, Indian Express, Udayvani, Vijayavani, Prajavani, Samyuktha Karnataka, Maliyalam Manorama.

UNIT IV: Development of Kannada Journalism

Hermann Moegling, M Venkatakrishnaiah, T T Sharma, Mohare Hanumantha Rao, DV Gundappa. Major Kannada Dailies: Samyukta Karnataka, Prajavani, Kannada Prabha, Udayavani, Vijaya Karnataka. Tabloids in Kannada. The present status of Kannada Journalism.

UNIT V: Word Processing:

Open, Save and Close Word Document; Editing Text, Tools, Formatting, Bullets, Spell Checker, Navigating in Word; Keyword, Mouse, Document Formatting; Paragraph Alignment, Indentation, Headers and Footers, Numbering, Printing, Preview Options, Templates and Wizards, Table and Contents and Indexes, Tables and Columns.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Jeffrey, Robin. (2003). *India's newspaper revolution: Capitalism, politics and the Indian-language Press*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Kumar, J Keval. (2003). *Mass communication in India*. Delhi: Jaico Publishing House.
- Murthy, Nadiga Krishna. (1966). *Indian journalism*. Mysore: Prasaraanga, Mysore University.
- Natarajan, J. (2017). *History of Indian journalism*. New Delhi: Publications Division, Govt. of India:
- Parthasarathy, Rangaswami. (2001). *Journalism in India* (4th Ed). New Delhi: Sterling Publishers
- RNI (Annual) *Press in India*. Government of India. Available at rni.nic.in

20BAJ32: ADVERTISING

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: to develop creative solutions to address advertising and marketing communications challenges.

UNIT I: Advertising

definition – origin and development of advertising – social and economic effects of advertising – Advertising agency structure and functions.

UNIT II: Varies types of Advertisements

Types of advertising – classifieds – retail—display –corporate – industrial product – public service advertising, political advertising.

UNIT III: Making of an Advertisement

Advertising production – copy writing – types of copy –layout –headline - colour – illustrations.

UNIT IV: Ad Campaign

Advertising campaigns – planning –positioning -media selection – Print, radio, TV, outdoor, direct mail, new media – Marketing mix.

UNIT V: Law and ethics in advertising

Consumerism and media – Code of Ethics in advertising ASCI– ABC. Accreditation of advertising agencies.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Barzman, A. (2004). *Radio Advertising*. Chandigarh: Unistar Books Pvt Ltd
- Batra, Rajeev. (1996). *Advertising management*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- Chaudhuri, Arun. (2014). *Indian advertising: Laughter and tears-1950-2013*. New Delhi: Niyogi Books.
- Chunawalla, S A and Sethia, K. C. (2006). *Foundations of advertising theory and practice*. (6th ed.) New Delhi: Himalaya.
- Cluley, Robert. (2017). *Essentials of advertising*. New York: Kogan Page.
- Dennison, D. (1999). *The Advertising Hand Book*. Mumbai: Jaico Publishing House.
- Jefkins, Frank. (2016). *Advertising made simple*. London: Heinemann.
- Young, Miles. (2018). *Ogilvy on advertising in the digital age*. New York: Bloomsberg Publishers

20BAJ33: PRODUCT & BRAND MANAGEMENT
4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: to learn fundamentals of Product and Brand Management. The aim of Product Management Part is to make participants understand competition at product level as well as brand level.

UNIT I: PRODUCT MANAGEMENT

Introduction to Product Management, Marketing mix and product mix, the changing dimensions, Product and growth strategies, managing line extension, assessing new competition and strategic response.

UNIT II: MARKET PLANNING

Introduction to Market Planning, components to market planning and competition defined, Competition based and study of competitor, Competitor analysis, customer analysis, market potential and sales forecasting.

UNIT III: BRANDING

Introduction of Branding, Concept of Branding, Definition of Brand, Brand name, Image, Identity and leverage, Brand creation and Brand building.

UNIT IV: BRAND IMAGE AND BRAND POSITIONING

Brand image, Dimension of brand image, brand association, corporate image, Brand identity, composition of brand identity. brand personality.

UNIT V: BRAND POSITIONING AND BRAND EQUITY

Brand positioning introduction, meaning, evaluation and choice of positioning and Brand equity objective, introduction and consequents of brand equity.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Product Policy and Brand Management- Chitale A. K
- New Product and Brand Management Prentice Halls -Gary L Lilien, Arvind Rangaswamy
- Product and Brand Management- U. C. Mathur
- Brand Management- Philip Kotler
- Strategy and Management of Industrial Brands- Malaval, Philippe
- International Corporate Brand Management - Meierer, Markus

20BAJ34: FEATURE WRITING

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Student will learn the skills necessary to succeed at any magazine as well as other journalistic environments. It is useful to add sizzle and write feature stories of various types, including profiles, news features, how-to articles, essays, reviews, service pieces, interactive narratives, special reports and whatever we can dream up.

UNIT I: Features

definition and scope, types of features – news features, personality features, scientific features, how-to-do-it features, travel features, lifestyle features, business features, human interest features, historical features, Institutional features and ad features.

UNIT II: Structure of feature stories

headlines, feature leads: types of leads, characteristics of feature writing. Differences between features and news story, features and articles.

UNIT III: Writings

Feature stories, articles, profiles, obituaries, editorials, travel writing. Trends in features writing.

UNIT IV: Pages

Column - types of columns, columnists, cartoons, comic strips, feature syndicates, freelancing

UNIT V: Writing reviews

Theories of criticism, principles of criticism and reviewing, writing of book reviews, film reviews, theatre reviews, art reviews.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Brian Nicholas (1972). Features with Flair, Vikas Publications, India
- Todd Hunt (1972). Reviewing for the Mass Media, Chilton Book, Southborough
- Brendan Hennessy (2006). Writing Feature and Articles, Taylor & Francis, U.K
- Louis Alexander (1975). Beyond the facts: A Guide to the Art of Feature Writing, Gulf Publishing Co, Houston
- Hake Mulder Jan R, Acde Jonge Fay & Singh P.P (2002). Professional Journalism, Anmol Publications Pvt Ltd, New Delhi.
- Shrivastava K.M (2003). News Reporting and Editing, Sterling Publishers, New Delhi
- Peter Dahlgren and Colin Sparks (1992). Journalism and Popular Culture, Sage publication, India.
- Jay Friedlander & John Lee (1993). Feature Writing for Magazines and Newspapers, HarperCollins, India.
- Julian Harris, Kelly, B Leiter & Stanley Johnson (1981). The Kingdom.
- Robert Gunning (1968). Techniques of Clear Writing, McGraw Hill, United States.

20BAJ35: HUMAN RIGHTS JOURNALISM

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: This course aims to critically consider traditional human rights, concerns regarding the media and current debates regarding the role played by the media within the field of human rights.

UNIT I: Introduction to IC

Introduction to the Constitution of India, Preamble to the Indian Constitution, Fundamental Rights and its limitations, Directive Principles of the State Policy and fundamental duties

UNIT II: Human Rights

Origin and history of Human rights, Human rights organizations of the World and in India, Types of Human rights, understanding the state of Human rights today

UNIT III: Media and Human Rights

Media and Human Rights, introduction to Women's Human Rights, International and Indian Human Right Movements, Media coverage of Human Rights

UNIT IV: Human rights and news stories

Human rights and Human-interest stories, Reporting Human Rights stories for Newspaper, Websites. Blogging as a medium of activism

UNIT V: Media and Laws

Right to Information Act, RTI activists and Whistle blowers, Whistle Blowers Act, Article 19, 1(a), Article 66(a), Article 377, applying for RTI, citizen journalism
Leila Seth (2015) *Talking of Justice: Peoples Rights in Modern India*, Aleph Book Company

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- *Handbook of Human Rights and Criminal Justice in Indi : The System and Procedure (English) 3rd Edition-* South Asia Human Rights Documentation Center
- **Sudhir Naib (2013),***The Right to Information in India*, oxford University press
- Kashyap, C, Subhash (2006) *Constitution of India: Review and Reassessment*, Universal Law Publishers
- Basu, Durga Das (2008) *Constitutional Law of India*, Lexis Nexis, Nagpur
- Jain, MP (2010) *Indian Constitutional Law*, Lexis Nexis, Nagpur

20BAJ36: MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: This Provides the knowledge of contemporary issues related to the field of managing information systems, develop knowledge and skills required to work effectively in a profession, enhance self-confidence, ability to make proper decisions and effective communication

UNIT I: THE MEANING AND ROLE OF MIS

What is MIS? Decision support systems, systems approach, the systems view of business, MIS Organization within the company. Management Organizational theory and the systems approach: Development of organization theory, management and organizational behaviour.

UNIT II: DATABASE MANAGEMENT

What the Manager Should Know about Computer Systems: Data processing and the computer, Operation of a manual Information System, Components of a computer system, Conversion of manual to computer-based system. Database Management: The business settings, Objects of DBMS, Database Technical overview.

UNIT III: INFORMATION SYSTEMS FOR DECISION MAKING

Evolution of an information system, Basic Information Systems, decision making and MIS, MIS as a technique for making programmed decisions, decision assisting information systems. Strategic and project planning for MIS: General business planning, appropriate MIS response.

UNIT IV: CONCEPTUAL SYSTEM DESIGN

Define the problems, set system objectives, establish system constraints, determine information needs, determine information sources, develop alternative conceptual designs and select one, document the system concept

UNIT V: IMPLEMENTATION, EVALUATION AND MAINTENANCE OF THE MIS

Plan the implementation, acquire floor space and plan space layouts, organize for implementation, develop procedures for implementation, train and operating personnel, computer related acquisitions, develop forms for data collection and information, dissemination, develop the files, test the system, cut over, document the system, evaluate the MIS, control and maintain the system.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Information Systems for Modern Management - R. G. Murdick, J. E. Ross and J. R. Clagget.
- Management Information System: Strategy & Action- Parker, Charles Case, Thomas
- Management Information Systems - O' Brien James A
- Management Information Systems - Sadagopan S
- Management Information Systems - Murdic and Ross
- Systems Analysis for Business - Optner

IV Semester

20BAJ41 ELECTRONIC JOURNALISM

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: This course intends to teach Audio - Video production techniques and to understand Radio, TV and Cinema as a powerful mass media.

UNIT I Evolution of Radio.

AM and FM radio. Public service broadcasting and commercial broadcasting

UNIT II All India Radio

All India Radio: Vividh Bharathi & Private FM. Nature and functions community radio. Types of Radio programmes- News, current affairs, external service, special audience programmes

UNIT III Television

Evolution of Doordarshan, national and regional programmes, emergence of satellite and cable TV channels

UNIT IV: TV Channels

Types of television channels, news, entertainment, sports, education, children and business channels. Growth of Kannada television channels – news and entertainment channels in Kannada

UNIT V: Cinema

Evolution of cinema, development of cinema in India and Karnataka, popular and new wave cinema, status of Indian cinema, FTII, NFAI

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Bhatt, S.C. (2007). *Broadcast journalism: Basic principles*. New Delhi: Har-Anand.
- Chatterji, Shoma A (2014) *100 Years of jump-cuts and fade-outs : Tracking change in Indian cinema*. New Delhi: Rupa Publ
- Chatterji, P C. (1991). *Broadcasting In India*, 2nd Edition. New Delhi: Sage
- Publications. Dijk, Jan van. (2006). *The network society: Social aspects of new media*. New Delhi: Sage.
- Saran R (2012) *History of Indian cinema*. New Delhi: Diamod Pocket Books.
- Sari, Anil. (2011). *Indian cinema: The faces behind the masks*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Shrivastava, K M. (2005). *Broadcast journalism: in the 21st century*. New Delhi
- Sterling. Usharani, N. (2006). *Educational Television in India*. New Delhi: Discovery.

20BAJ42 NEW MEDIA TECHNOLOGY

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: This course explores basic concepts of new media as well as the role digital media (aka “new media”) technologies play in society. Students will use digital media technology throughout the course, providing them with practical experience with new media.

UNIT – I: Introduction to New Media Technology

Emergence of New Communication Technologies, Characteristics, Global Village, Globalization, Satellite Television.

UNIT – II: Applications of ICT

ARPANET, Internet, Search Engines, Web Radio and TV, Technological Convergence, ICT and Information Society; Factors Influencing Information Society, Theories of Information Society, Knowledge Society, WSIS Summit on Information Society.

UNIT – III: Issues in New Media Technology

Electronic Governance, Information Super-Highway, Leaf Frogging, Digital Divide, ICT Grass-Roots Initiatives, New Technology Innovations, Case Studies.

UNIT – IV: Forms of New Media:

Web Journalism, Journalists and the Internet, Electronic Publishing, Virtual Reality, Information Technology Act 2000.

UNIT – V: Content Developing for Internet Medium

Web - Designing, Web Page, HTTP, HTML, Software Applications; Photoshop, MS Windows Application, Page Maker, In-Design.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- AMIC: Public Service Broadcasting in Asia
- Denis Macquill: Mass Communication Theory
- F.E. Davis, J.A Barry - L.W. Hall: Newsletter Publishing with Page Maker.
- Rogers Cadenhead: Front Page.
- Orbicom: New Partnership in Communications for the 21st Century: Orbicom.
- Rick Altman: Quark Express for Windows
- Chetan Srivastava: Introduction to Information Technology
- Santhosh Choubey, Ramprasad: An Introduction to Information Technology and Computer Fundamental.

20BAJ43: E - BUSINESS

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Presents concepts and skills for the strategic use of e-commerce and related information technology from three perspectives: business to consumers, business-to-business, and intra-organizational.

UNIT I: E-BUSINESS FRAMEWORK

Definition, Origin, History of Internet, Working of E-Business, Advantages and Disadvantages, E-Business v/s Traditional Business Mechanism, E-Business opportunities for Business, Goal of E-Business.

UNIT II: E-BUSINESS TECHNOLOGY AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Economic Theories of E-Business, Business -to-consumer (B2C) systems and strategies, Business-to-Business (B2B) models and strategies, Implication of E-Business strategies, Business Applications: Consumer-oriented and Business-oriented E-Business.

UNIT III: E-BUSINESS PAYMENTS

Introduction to Electronic Payment Systems (EPS), Types of E-Payments: Credit Cards, Smart cards, E-Cash/ Cyber cash, E-cheque, Micro Payment Systems, Characteristics of Electronic Payment systems, Need of EPS System.

UNIT IV: INTERNET ENVIRONMENT OF E-COMMERCE

Introduction, E-Commerce Security Environment, Security concerns, Types of security vulnerabilities in E-Business, Internet Economy Conceptual Framework, Providers and Vendors of E-Business Software.

UNIT V: E-COMMERCE IN INDIA

State of e-business in India, problems and opportunities in e-commerce in India, legal issues and Challenges in Indian Perspective, Role of e- business in India Scope and future of e-business, Impact of e-business on market and retailers and its social impact

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- E Business R(Evolution) - Daniel Amor, Pearson Edude.
- E-Commerce Management – Krishnamurthy
- E-Commerce: Strategy, Technologies and Applications - David Whiteley
- E-Commerce: A managerial Perspectives - P. T. Joseph
- The Complete E- Commerce Book - Jaince Reynolds
- Beginning Ruby on Rails: E- Commerce - JarkkoLaine.

20BAJ44: GLOBAL BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: An understanding of the manner in which different forms of economic systems sustain high levels of productivity and living standards and to know how the role of managers varies across different forms of economic systems.

UNIT I: Globalisation

Emerging global economy- Globalization of production- Drivers of Globalization, advantages and disadvantages of Globalization- Globalization: policy Issues, Measures towards Globalization, Technology and Global competitiveness.

UNIT II: INTERNATIONAL TRADE AND PAYMENTS

Government influence on international Trade- Foreign Trade Policy- Counter Trade, Global Sourcing- Theories of International Trade- Mercantilism, Theory of Absolute cost advantage, Comparative Cost Advantage Theory, Product Life Cycle theory, global Strategic Rivalry Theory and Porter`s national competitive advantage theory. Balance of payment- Meaning.

UNIT III: MULTILATERAL REGULATIONS AND FOREIGN TRADE PROCEDURES

General Agreement on Tariff and Trade (GATT) - Establishment of WTO- Organization structure of WTO, Uruguay round package. United Nations Conference on trade and Development (UNCTAD), Export Procedures- Import Procedures.

UNIT IV: TRADE BLOCKS AND BUSINESS CENTRES

Economic integration- European Union- North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA)- The Association of South-East Asian Nations (ASEAN)- European Free Trade Association- South Asian Association for regional cooperation (SAARC)

UNIT V: CONFLICTS, NEGOTIATIONS, CONTROLLING AND EVALUATION OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

Introduction- Factors causing Conflicts- Conflict between Host Country and Transnational Company- Negotiations- Role of International agencies in Conflict Resolution. Control of MNCs.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- | | | |
|--------------------------------------|---|--------------------|
| • Global Business Management | - | Adhikary, Manab |
| • International Business | - | VyuptakeshSharan |
| • International Business | - | P. SubbaRao |
| • International Business Environment | - | Francis Cherunilam |
| • International Business | - | Daniels |
| • International business | - | Rao and rangachari |

20BAJ45: PHOTO JOURNALISM

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: To develop in the student the skill, techniques and art of capturing the essence of a story in a photograph. How to use a camera to capture the "moment" or event to enhance a news story or to stand alone as a visual statement. To shoot photos for newspapers, magazines, public relations and other media.

UNIT – I Introduction to Photography:

Nature and Scope of Photography, Evolution of Photography, Photography as an Art Form, Elements of Camera, Types of Camera, Digital Photography, Types of Lenses, Filters, Lighting Devices, Photo Processing and Editing Software's.

UNIT – II Techniques of Photography:

Composition and Camera Control Devices, ISO, Aperture and Shutter Speed, Attributes of a Good Picture, Black and White and Colour Photography.

UNIT – III Branches of Photography:

Life, Landscape, Wildlife, Sports, Environment, Portraiture, Travel, Press Photography, Wedding and Candid Photography.

UNIT – IV Fields of Photojournalism:

Spot News, general news, Street Photography, off-beat photography, and documentary photography, war, terror, and crime. Photographs for photo features, photo stories and photo essays. Developing specialisations like sports, portrait, art and culture, environment, and industry, aerial, candid, fashion, food, environmental, forensic, medical, paparazzi, nature, and underwater

UNIT – V Photo Journalism:

Definition, Nature and Scope of Photo Journalism, Evolution of Press Photography, Source of News Photographs, News/Photo Agencies, Caption Writing, Legal and Ethical Aspects of Photography.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Rothsteline A: Photo Journalism
- Rhode and Mcneal: Press Photography
- Cyernsheim G.H: History of Photography
- Jack Price: News Photography
- Midwest Magnet: Photography and Printed World
- The National Press Photographers Association, USA: Photo Journalism.
- Calder, Julian and Garret J: New 35mm Photographer's Handbook
- Allyn Salomon: Advertising Photography
- Peter Tausk: An Introduction to Press Photography
- Logan H. Richard: Elements of Photo Reporting
- Erickson B. And Romano F.: Professional Digital Photography

20BAJ46: MEDIA LAW
4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Media law is a course that seeks a co-relationship of the constitutional objective of free expression and speech and also the restrictions and rights governing the fourth estate.

UNIT I: IC and Media

Salient features of the Indian Constitution – fundamental rights and duties – Article 19-1 (a) and (2) - freedom of the press

UNIT II: Laws relating to media

Press and Registration of Books Act – Working Journalists Act – Law of Defamation–contempt of court – contempt of legislature

UNIT III: Media Laws and Acts

Right to information Act –Copyrights Act – Intellectual Property Rights. Cyber law – Cable television network (regulation) Act – film censorship

UNIT IV: Media Institutions

Major recommendations of the first and second press commissions, Press Council of India Act, a critical study of functions and performance of the Press Council of India

UNIT V: Media Ethics

Media's ethical problems- Sting operation, Right to privacy, sensationalism and yellow journalism, paid news, Media self-regulation: BCCC, Ombudsman.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Basu, Durga Das. (2010). *Law of the press*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India.
- Myneni, S.R. (2015). *Media law*. Hyderabad: Asia Law House.
- Pathak, Juhi P. (2014). *Introduction to mass media laws and ethics*. Delhi.
- Shipra Publication. Neelamalar, M. (2009). *Media law and ethics*. Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.
- Prasad, Kiran. (2011). *Media law in India*. Delhi: Kluwer Law International.
- Divan, Madhavi Goradia. (2018). *Facets of Medial Law*. New Delhi: Eastern Book Company.

V Semester

20BAJ51: PUBLIC RELATION

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: This course intends to expose students with the creative and management aspects of Public Relations. The course includes planning and execution of Public Relations campaigns.

UNIT I: Public relations

Public relations – definition – nature, scope and functions – origin and development of PR in India. PR Process – fact finding, planning, implementation and evaluation

UNIT II: Ad & PR

Differences among advertising, publicity, propaganda- public opinion- responsibilities of a PR practitioner

UNIT III: Tools of PR

Tools of PR – print, radio, film, television, new media, photography, house journals, exhibitions, Open House

UNIT IV: PR and Media

Types of public relations – government, private, public sector, community relations, employee relations, media relations- PR in democracy

UNIT V: Problems and prospects of PR.

Problems and prospects of PR. Event management, Code of ethics in PR – professional organizations: PRSI-PRCI – IPRA

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Bhimani, Rita. (2018). PR2020: The trending practice of public relations.
- New Delhi: BEE Books. Reddy, C.V. Narasiman. (2014). *Effective public relations and media strategy* (92nd edition). Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.
- Sachdeva.S.Iqbal. (2009). Public Relations: Principles and Practices. New Delhi: Oxford University Express.
- Sardana, C.K. (2000) Applied public relations in the Indian context. New Delhi: Harananda Publicaitons.
- Scott, David Meerman. (2010). *The new rules of marketing and PR*. Hoboken
- John Wiley & Sons c. Singh J.K. (2007). *Media and public relations*. New Delhi: Kul Bhushan Nangia APH
- Smith. D. Ronald. (2009). *Strategic planning for public Relations*. New York: Routledge.
- Solis, Brain & Brackenridge, Deirdre. (2009). *Putting the Public Back in Public Relations*. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Education

20BAJ52: BASIC MEDIA RESEARCH

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Media Research will entail deeper understanding in evaluating current practices across different verticals of media and communication using predefined methodologies and objectives

UNIT - I

Basic Concepts: Definition, Nature and Scope of Communication Research; Development of Mass Media Research, Characteristics of Research; Evaluation of Communication Research in India, Elements of Research, Research Process.

UNIT - II

Research Approaches: Qualitative Research Method; Field Observations, Focus Groups, Case Studies, Quantitative Methods; Content Analysis, Survey Research, Sample and Sampling Techniques, Reliability and Validity

UNIT - III

Tools of Data Collection: Questionnaire, Interview Schedule, Levels of Measurement, Measures of Central Tendencies, Tests of Significance.

UNIT – IV

Data Analysis Techniques: Coding and Tabulation, Non-Statistical Methods, Descriptive, Historical, Statistical Analysis, Parametric and Non-Parametric, Tests of Significance, Rating Scales, SPSS and Other Statistical Packages.

UNIT – V

Preparation of Research Reports: Ethical Perspective of Mass Media Research, Trends in Communication Research, Abstract Writing, Manuscript, writing a Research Report, Concluding the Research Report, Bibliography and References, Research Journals.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Winner and Dominic: Mass Media Research
- Ralph Nafzieger & David M. White: Introduction to Mass Communication Research
- Robert B. Burns: Introduction to Research Methods.
- O R Krishnaswamy: Methodology of Research in Social Science
- Stempel and Westley: Research Methods in Mass Communication
- David M. Nachmias & Chava Nachmias: Research in Social Science
- Lewis - Beck: Basic Statistics
- Bower & Courtright: Communication Research Method
- Dennis MC quill: Milestones in Mass Communication Research

20BAJ53: FILM PRODUCTION

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Cinema studies deals with various aspects of cinema in technical and analytical terms including history, relevance and role in society and perceptions among the masses. Students will be able to understand the complete process of cinema making and also appreciate the greatest films and makers of all times.

UNIT I: History of Cinema

Brief history of cinema, Lumiere brothers, attempt to capture moving images, cinematographe, the era of silent movies, early films in Europe, History of Indian Cinema

UNIT II: Aspects of Cinema

Talkies, voice recording for cinema, George Millis's Trip to the Moon, Dziga Vertov's Man with a Moving Camera, special effects in early cinema

UNIT III: Technical aspects of Cinema

Camera Movement, script, screen play and montage, the importance of cinematic medium, great masters of world cinema, alternate and parallel cinema, Aurthur Theory, Feminist film Theory, Formalist film theory

UNIT IV: Documentary

Introduction to Documentary films, history of documentaries, grammar of Documentary films, few examples of Documentary

UNIT V: Digitalisation in Cinema

Digital technology in Cinema, concepts of digital editing, digital correction of colors, manipulations, possible opportunities and limitations

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Braudy, Leo & Mrshall, Cohen (Eds) (1999) *Film Theory and Criticism-5thed*, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Nichols, Bill (Eds)(1993) *Movies and Method*. Vol.1&2. Calcutta, Seagull Books.
- Giannetti, Lousi(1993) *Understanding Movies*, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Gledhill, Christen & Williams, Linda, *Reinventing Film Studies*, London; Arnold Publishers.
- Nelmes, Jill (1996) *An Introduction to Film Studies*, New York: Routledge.

20BAJ54: MAGAZINE JOURNALISM

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: Print media has various formats while informing its masses. Magazines are effective ways to inform and act as memory retainers for its audiences. The course will elucidate the different departments concerned when magazine becomes a player in the information selling market. Students will also learn the extreme differences in writing and working for a magazine as against traditional and digital journalism.

UNIT I: Magazine

Introduction to Magazine Journalism, evolution of Magazine Journalism, classifications of Magazines, Magazine Industry, Major national and international Magazines

UNIT II: Trends in Magazine

Recent trends in Magazine Journalism, web-based magazines, E-Zines and web zines, writing for magazine, difference between writing for magazine and writing for newspaper, Magazine features, alternative classification of Magazine features

UNIT III: Process of Magazine

Magazine editing, basics of Magazine productions, publishing Magazine online, cover page design, Magazine layout, use of pictures and graphics

UNIT IV: Contents on Magazine

Reporting cover stories and crime stories for magazines, magazine circulation and readership, ownership of magazines

UNIT V: Magazines Today

Business and revenue models of magazines, magazine scenario in India, designing and printing a magazine

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Jill, Baker (1992) *Professional Magazine Journalism*, Blue Print Publishers
- Jacobi P. Peter (1991) *The Magazine Article - How to Think it, Plan it, Write it*, Bloomington, Indiana University Press
- McKay, Jenny (2006) *The Magazine Handbook*, Oxon, Routledge
- Niblock, Sarah (2003), *Inside Journalism*, London, Routledge
- Davis Anthony (1988) *Magazine Journalism Today*, Heinemann Professional Publishing, Indiana University Mogel,
- Leonard (1998) *Everything You Need to Know to Make It in the Magazine Business*, Pittsburgh, GATF Press.
- Holmes, Tim (2008), *Mapping the Magazine: Comparative Studies in Magazine Journalism*, Routledge

20BAJ55 Television Production

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective: The course is intended to prepare students to handle basic video production, responsibilities with a fair amount of confidence and conviction. It also revolves around aesthetics and grammar of television keeping in mind the technical skills the student needs to acquire.

UNIT I : Television Production

Introduction to television production, characteristics and functions of a TV camera, the lens system, controlling the lens system, the viewfinder, image sensors, indicators, audio polls, camera controls and movements

UNIT II: Camera Movements

Different types of shots, composition and framing of shots, rule of thirds and crossing the line, white balance, iris, focus of the camera

UNIT III: Lightings

Basics of lighting, importance of lighting, hard light, soft light, three-point Lighting, color temperature, shooting in the day light, shooting in low light

UNIT IV: Audio and Scripting

Sound for television, audio recording and acoustics for television, basic editing for television, editing principles, cutting points, transitions and concepts of continuity, scripting for television, research for scripting and story boarding

UNIT V: Production Stage

Indoor and outdoor shooting, voiceover and dubbing, post production, production management, logistics, equipment care and collection

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Jarvis, Peter (1998) *The Essential TV Director's Handbook*, Oxford, Focal Press.
- Bignell, Jonathan and Orlebar, Jeremy (2005) *The Television Handbook*. - 3rded, Oxon, Routledge.
- Zettl (2000) *Television Production Handbook* -7th, NewYork, Wadsworth.
- Gerald Millerson (1992) *Video Production Handbook*. -2NDed, Oxford, Focal Press.
- Gerald Millerson (1993) *Effective TV Production*. -3rded, Oxford, Focal Press.

20BAJ56 ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT

4 Credits, 40 Hours, 100 Marks

Objective The objective of entrepreneurial development is to motivate a person for entrepreneurial career and to make him capable of perceiving and exploiting successfully opportunities for enterprises.

UNIT I: INTRODUCTION TO ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Meaning-Concept of Entrepreneurship -History of Entrepreneurship Development - Role of Entrepreneurship in Indian economic development with reference to Self-employment development. -Agencies in Entrepreneurship Management – Future of Entrepreneurship Management - Concept of Entrepreneurship Development-Entrepreneur Vs Intrapreneur -Entrepreneur Vs. Entrepreneurship- Entrepreneur Vs. Manager -Attributes and Characteristics of successful Entrepreneur

UNIT II: BUSINESS OPPORTUNITY IDENTIFICATION AND BUSINESS PLAN

Business Idea-Method of generating idea and opportunity recognition- Preparing Business Plan- Meaning -Significance of Business Plan-Components of Business Plan-Business Planning Process.

UNIT III: PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Technical -Financial- Marketing-Personnel and Management Feasibility- Estimating Financing Funds requirements –Functions and Schemes offered by various commercial banks and financial institutions like IDBI, ICICI, SIDBI, SFC's.

UNIT IV: ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT AND GOVERNMENT

Role of Central Government and State Government in promoting Entrepreneurship-Introduction to various incentives-Subsidies and Grants Export Oriented Units- Fiscal and Tax concessions available-Role of following agencies in the Entrepreneurship Development- District Industries Centers- Small Industries-Service Industries. - Entrepreneurship Development of India-National Institute of Entrepreneurship and small business development.

UNIT V: WHY DO ENTREPRENEUR FAIL AND ENTREPRENEURIAL PITFALLS

Role of Entrepreneurship Qualities of Successful Entrepreneurs-Risk faced by the Present Entrepreneur, Reasons for Low/ No Entrepreneurs- Women Entrepreneurs: Role -Problems -Prospects- Social entrepreneurship- Concepts - Importance- Barriers in Entrepreneurship.

BOOKS FOR REFERENCE:

- Entrepreneurial Development -Vasanth Desai
- Small and Medium Enterprises in India -Indian Institute of Banking and Finance
- Essentials of Business Environment & Entrepreneurship -Aswathappa K
- Support System for Entrepreneurs - Moulik T.K
- Government as Entrepreneur - Albert. N

